

The Significant and Profound Impacts of Gordon Life Science Institute

Short Communication

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The "Gordon Life Science" or "GLS" Institute is the first Internet Institute in the world. Established by Prof. Dr. Kuo-Chen Chou in 2003, right after he was retired from "Pfizer Global Research and Development" in San Diego, California.

There is a very interesting story for the name of Institute as elaborated below.

After the "gangs of four" (including Mao Zedong's wife) was smashed and the complete failure of Mao "Cultural Revolution", China was under the leadership of Deng Xiaoping, who took the policy of "韬光养晦" starting to open China's door, the founder was invited by Professor Sture Forsén, the then "Chairman of Nobel Prize Committee", to work in Chemical Center of Lund University as a Visiting Professor. It was very difficult for Swedish people to pronounce "Kuo-Chen Chou". In order for his colleagues and friends there easier to pronounce his name, Professor Chou used "Gordon" as his name in Sweden.

In 2003, about a quarter of century later, the same name was used for the Institute, meaning that Deng's "韬光养晦" policy can stimulate a lot of great creativities.

Accordingly, strictly speaking, it is in "Lund of Sweden" where the "Gordon Life Science Institute" has already been of pregnancy. But after 30 years in 2003, the Institute has been really born in San Diego of California. And its current liaison site is in Boston of Massachusetts. For more information about the Institute, click the button at <https://gordonlifescience.org/GordonLifeScience.html>.

The Institute is superior to any of the conversional institutes in both the number of the publications and their novelty (see, e.g., [1-341]).

Up to March, 2019, the Institute has 26 members. Among them 5 have been selected by Thompson Reuter and Clarivate Analyt-

ics as the "Highly Cited Researcher" or "HCR": (1) Xoan Xiao (2018), (2) Hao Lin (2018), (3) Wei Chen (2018), (4) Hong-Bin Shen (2014 and 2015), and (5) Kuo-Chen Chou for continuously 5 years (2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, and 2018), indicating that for the ratio of HCR per member, the "Gordon Life Science Institute" has already exceeded the "Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard, USA", becoming the very top in the world.

Particularly, facing the Pandemic COVID-2019, the Gordon Life Science Institute has the overwhelming advantages to the conventional Institutions or Institutes.

It is indeed a very important strategy to develop the Internet Institutes such as "Gordon Life Science Institute", and it is indeed very profound as well for saving our planet.

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Received: November 21, 2020

Accepted: November 22, 2020

Published: November 23, 2020

Citation: Kuo-Chen Chou. The Significant and Profound Impacts of Gordon Life Science Institute. *Int J Genomics Proteomics Metabolomics Bioinformatics.* 2020;3(1):43-50.

doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2577-4336-200008>

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